

THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF IRON PYRITES

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Thermal decomposition of iron pyrites (500°-800°); shows that by application of heat alone only half of the sulphur content of the ore is liberated.

That iron pyrites, when heated in absence of air, liberates sulphur, was known for a long time. Marchal (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1924, *iv*, 35, 43) observed that the dissociation of iron pyrites (into ferrous sulphide and sulphur) in vacuum began at 500° and was complete in 2 hours at 850°. At higher temperatures (1200°) she detected the presence of a small amount of iron. X-ray investigations by de Jong and Willems (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 161, 311) showed that the reaction took place according as $2\text{FeS}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{FeS} + \text{S}_2$. D'Or (*Compt. rend.*, 1930, 190, 1296; *J. chim. phys.*, 1930, 27, 239; 1931, 28, 377) supported Jong and Willems' views on the mechanism of dissociation by means of spectroscopic analyses. Udintzeva and Tschufarov (*J. Appl. Chem. Russia*, 1941, 14, 3) has pointed out that the velocity of the reaction $\text{FeS}_2 \rightarrow \text{FeS} + \text{S}$ is, within certain limits, proportional to the temperature and inversely proportional to the diameter of the particles and the pressure. In a previous communication, Chowdhury and Hussain (*J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. & News Ed.*, 1945, 8, 81) discussed the results of dry chlorination of iron pyrites between 500° and 800°. The purpose of the present investigation was to ascertain the rôle played by chlorine and the dissociation of the pyrites within the range of the experiment. The dissociation reaction was carried out under conditions exactly the same as that of chlorination.

EXPERIMENTAL

The tube containing the ore (10 g.) being kept in position as usual, the air inside the tube was completely displaced by carbon dioxide. This being ensured, the carbon dioxide supply was cut off and the temperature of the furnace was raised to the desired degree, and kept constant for 6 hours. The elementary sulphur, set free, collected in the cooler parts of the tube. After the reaction, the elementary sulphur was dissolved out with carbon disulphide and estimated. The residual ore was digested and the total sulphur in it estimated. The total of the elementary sulphur liberated and the residual sulphur in the ore were always found short of the total sulphur input by 3 to 4%. This was supposed mainly due to the loss incurred in collecting the sulphur from the tube. Taking the dissociation process as represented by the equation $\text{FeS}_2 \rightarrow \text{FeS} + \text{S}$, it is easy to see that half the amount of total sulphur, initially contained in the portion of the ore undergoing dissociation, comes out as elementary sulphur. So the extent of the dissociation is given by doubling the percentage of the elementary sulphur formed. The results obtained are tabulated below.

TABLE I
Dissociation under normal atmospheric pressure.
 Ore taken—10 g. (40–60 mesh).

Temp.	Yield of elem. S	Unreacted S.	Total S accounted for.	% Dissociation.
500°	2.21%	96.00%	98.21%	4.42
550°	6.01	90.58	96.59	12.02
600°	34.12	62.80	96.92	68.24
700°	39.57	56.82	96.39	79.14
800°	42.97	52.92	95.89	85.94

The percentage dissociation when plotted against temperature (fig. not shown) shows that the extent of dissociation sharply changes between 550° and 600°. Below 550°, the dissociation is practically nil, at 600° the percentage is considerably high. This again increases with temperature.

From the results it appears that with the application of heat alone, nearly half the total sulphur contained in the ore can be extracted by working at a temperature slightly higher than 800°. On a superficial view this may appear to be a very prospective way of extracting sulphur from pyrites. But a careful consideration shows that the observation is of little importance from an economic point of view. The residue of dissociation still contains half of the sulphur content of the ore, and the extraction of only half (simultaneously wasting the other half) cannot be expected to be economic.

And if the residue be later subjected to the action of chlorine to extract all the total sulphur content of the residue, the amount of chlorine necessary should be exactly the same as that required for chlorinating pyrites directly. This becomes evident from the following equations :

This inference from the stoichiometric relationship has also been confirmed by carrying out a few experiments in two steps.

It is interesting to note that the temperature (600°) at which the percentage dissociation suddenly becomes very high is also the temperature which is optimum for the chlorination of the ore for obtaining sulphur. The reasons for this coincidence are still obscure.

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